

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

	Theme	Working groups (active)
# 1	<i>Universal inflow characterisation</i>	(#1) Turbulence Intensity (TI) by Lidar (#2) Lidar Assisted Control (LAC)
# 2	<i>Replacing met masts</i>	(#3) Lidar in Complex Terrain (#4) Lidar in Cold Climate
# 3	<i>Connecting wind lidar</i>	(#5) Digitalization (#7) Lidar Ontology
# 4	<i>Accelerating offshore wind deployment</i>	(#6) Scanning Lidar Offshore

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

Key questions:

LiDAR data availability

- What are the reasons for low data availability in cold climate regions?
- Is there a way to increase data availability in cold climate regions?

Meteorological icing detection

- Are LiDAR suitable to detect meteorological icing?
- Is it possible to estimate ice classes from LiDAR data?

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

LiDAR data availability

- What are the reasons for low data availability in cold climate regions?
- Is there a way to increase data availability in cold climate regions?

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

LiDAR data availability

- What are the main factors affecting data availability?
- Is there a need for more data?

ZX300

regions?
regions?

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

LiDAR data availability
- What
- Is the

WC V2.1

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold cl

TECHNISCHES BÜRO FÜR ERNEUERBARE ENERGIE

Vergleichen
von Lil

A
IEA

Deep Learning Quality Control for Lidar Measurements

Andrew Black,
Research and
Applications Engineer,
Vaisala

Session

Resource assessment
Part 2

Understanding Pulsed Lidar Data Availability

Simulating with Reanalysis Data and Boosting with Convolutional Neural Networks
Andrew BLACK, Laurie PONTRÉAU, Pierre ALLAIN, Frederic DELBOS, Morgane KÉRAON, Mehdi MACHTA
Vaisala France

PO.164

Abstract

As wind energy development accelerates worldwide, many more campaigns are using onshore and offshore lidar, and more campaigns are occurring in locations with low aerosol density ("clean air" or "clear sky"). Lidar backscatter signals reduce lidar range and data availability and can lead to increased project uncertainty. This presentation will discuss (1) novel techniques to improve range and (2) novel techniques to improve range and data availability. (2) novel techniques to improve range and data availability. (2) novel techniques to improve range and data availability.

- New range data availability simulator using satellite and reanalysis data.
- Technique to maximize profiling lidar data availability with traditional algorithms.
- MosquitoNet, a new lidar range boosting technique based on a convolutional neural network.

Availability and Range Estimator

It is important to simulate the availability of a lidar before the campaign. The sensors in your observation network is a key detail in allocating resources. Vaisala's Data Availability and Range Estimator simulates lidar availability and range based on reanalysis data at the proposed measurement campaign.

14:15 - Enhancing
Wind Lidar Data
Availability:
Validation and
Application of the

S

Limitations on the use of lidar turbulence data for site suitability and energy yield assessment in complex sites.

Laura Valldecabres

Wind Resource Specialist, Enel Green Power

Floating LiDARs and Ever Increasing Hub Heights - How High is Too High?

Ela Young

Consultant Engineer, Frazer-Nash Consultancy

An IEA Task 52 analysis of LiDAR technology for measuring the wind in typical winter conditions as low aerosol concentration environments or fog

Sara Koller

Head of Wind&Ice, Meteotest

20-27 APRIL #W

Resource Assessment
Symposium

iea wind

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

Meteorological icing detection

- Are LiDAR suitable to detect meteorological icing?
- Is it possible to estimate ice classes from LiDAR data?

Icing detection with LiDAR

Winterwind 2023, Session Icing (4)

Sara Koller, Meteoest

March 28, 2023

The challenge of detecting the liquid water content with ceilometer and Wind LiDAR

Winterwind 2024, Session Environment (8)

Sara Koller, Fabian Umbricht, Meteoest
Pekko Tuominen, Vaisala

March 20, 2024

PO.100

Meteoest

The challenge of detecting the liquid water content with ceilometer and Wind LiDAR

Sara Koller¹, Pekko Tuominen², Fabian Umbricht¹
Meteoest¹, Vaisala²

A ceilometer of the new generation is able to detect the cloud type, which in combination with the temperature of a weather model or measurements on a met mast complete the information needed on the source of meteorological icing - the supercooled water droplets in clouds.

Framework

The analysis presented in this poster was realized within the IEA Wind TCP Task 52 Large-scale Deployment of Wind LiDAR by the working group LiDAR in Cold Climate.

The working group focuses on two key topics:
• Low data availability in cold climate regions
• Meteorological icing detection with LiDAR

Motivation and goal
In cold climate regions, knowledge of the frequency and duration of icing is of crucial importance, as icing leads to production losses that can be substantial. A method for detecting icing on several levels of the rotor plane does not yet exist. However, as blades collect ice along the entire rotor plane, this information is needed. The main cause of icing is clouds containing supercooled water droplets. We therefore need measuring devices that provide information on the presence of clouds, the consistency of the cloud and the temperature.

Measurement setup
Ceilometers are LiDARs that recognize cloud heights. The new generation of ceilometers is now able to identify the shape of the scatterer and thus determine whether it is a liquid cloud or an ice cloud.
The C&L ceilometer emits linearly polarized light. The polarization direction of the light changes depending on the shape of the scatterer.

→ Spheres: Due to the symmetry the detected return signal is not polarized.
→ Nonspheres: Significant depolarization due to multiple internal reflections at solid/fluid interfaces.
Next to the ceilometer a 100m met mast was installed, providing temperature and humidity measurements at 95m above ground.

Results
A low attenuated backscatter of a ceilometer in the range of $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ is typical for aerosol backscatter and can therefore be interpreted as clear sky (e.g. 8am – 9pm, Jan 14). Precipitation has a high attenuated backscatter of $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$ (e.g. 10pm, Jan 15 to 1am, Jan 16). Clouds have a very high backscatter in the range of $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1}$. The two periods on Jan 13 6.30am to 1.30pm and 7pm to 11.30pm show no ice to about 80m above ground.

Only with the information of the attenuated backscatter we do not know yet about the type of cloud or precipitation. This information can be derived from the depolarization. A depolarization ratio of 0.3 to 0.43 is typical for snowfall while a depolarization ratio of 0.01 to 0.2 applies to droplets. In our example, the precipitation event is therefore snow and the two cloud events are liquid clouds (precip.).

A ceilometer does not provide any information on temperature of the atmosphere. When looking at the isotherms of the COSMO-5 weather model from Meteoest's cold air is sinking in on Jan 14 at around 30m. The two periods with fog show temperatures of -6°C at 80m agl.

This is validated with the temperature and relative humidity measurements on the met mast at 95m. The ceilometer proves to be capable of giving rise-time height of clouds. The next step will be to calibrate the Wind LiDAR so that it provides the same.

Watch this presentation Download the poster

IEA Wind TCP – Task 52 General Meeting 2025

WG4 LiDAR in Cold climate

Deliverable:

Summary of the results obtained during the Task period in a short report

→ At the latest May 2026

Workshop Wednesday afternoon

